

Has that shape got a weight problem?

Understanding human/ object relationships through product elements: studying shape emotion and discourse using a Kelly's grid

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Abstract

This paper considers some implications of extending recent approaches to design and emotion from the level of the whole product to product elements. The shape of food cans is the element considered using the Kelly's grid technique. The paper first reviews approaches to the role of emotion in the relationship of people and objects, noting that approaches to emotion that stress its relational nature and encompass both its discursive and its embodied elements are likely to be particularly relevant to design. Then the process and results of the empirical research are described, describing the methods used and their relationship to emotion theory. Finally, this research is considered for what it indicates about appropriate relationships between a reductive approach to shape and emotion and a more 'holistic' approach that values the both the embodied and the discursive aspects of emotions, as well as acknowledging the insights available from both positive and negative emotions – disgust as well as delight.

Introduction

A good deal of work has emerged over the last decade that seeks to understand the affective aspect of consumers' relationship to material (and virtual) objects. Some of this work draws on the range of conceptualisations of emotion that exist to meet objectives that derive from design. Conceptualisations of emotion vary from the scientific perspectives found in psychology to the more humanistic views of emotion that emphasise its cultural aspects. The uses to which they have been put in design are as various and include making products more usable by increasing the likelihood that their users will feel pleasant emotions, even to the extent of joy (Green & Jordan 2001: 2); to increase products' lifespan by promoting the emotional attachment consumers can develop for objects by acknowledging the feelings of attachment that are evoked in our relationship to consumer products over their lifespan (Van Hinte 1997, Chapman 1997); to differentiate products aimed at small market segments from each other by capturing the emotion element of consumers' appraisal of product elements (Desmet Overbeeke and Tax 2001).

Alongside work by McDonagh-Philp and Lebbon (2000), Forlizzi, Disalvo and Hanington (2003), Norman (2004) and others, the Design community is likely to be most familiar with Desmet, Hekkert and Jakobs (2000) and Desmet, Overbeeke and Tax's (2001) framework for understanding the role emotion plays in consumers' experience of objects and designers are likely to readily connect with it because their work concentrates on appearance. This approach is thoroughly grounded in the psychology literature and allows designers to evaluate both the details of objects and the make up of groups of consumers for the likely emotional consequences of their interaction. As well as being attractive to designers because of its concern with appearance, their approach is likely to be especially relevant in the context of new product development. It is reductive, in that it screens out factors other than emotion in consumers' responses to objects, and in common with the approach to emotions found in the psychology literature (e.g. Russell 1980) it reduces emotions to a set that can be positioned spatially in relation to each other and represented visually, combining them with consumers' 'concerns'. It can integrate the aspect of design decision making that tolerates uncertainty (Rittel 1973, Cross 2001) and it demonstrates that it is viable to attend to the affective potential of the formal details of objects in relative isolation, as does the research described below.

However, this paper argues that such a reductive approach can only capture part of the emotional dimension of human/ object relationships, given Dewey's assertion (1980 (1934):

44, 69) that neither emotions themselves, nor the features of objects that elicit them can be truly understood in isolation. As Dewey puts it: 'Emotion is the moving and cementing force. It selects what is congruous and dyes what is selected with its color, thereby giving qualitative unity to materials externally disparate and dissimilar.' (1934: 44). He warns against 'erroneous' views of the nature of acts of expression which derive from the '...notion that an emotion is complete in itself within, only when uttered having impact on external material. But, in fact, an emotion is *to* or *from* or *about* something objective, whether in fact or in idea.' Italics in original (1934: 69). This paper shows that research into human/ object relationships which ignores the 'to, from and about' of emotion is likely to miss significant aspects of them. A tendency to the reductive – ignoring the 'to, from and about' of emotion - may be a significant methodological challenge for design based emotion research. Deborah Lupton's work confirms the impression that a reductive approach ignores aspects of emotions that are potentially necessary to a full understanding of interactions with objects. She identifies a spectrum of theoretical approaches to emotion that ranges from the 'biologic' to the 'constructed', the former reducing emotions to qualities of our physical make-up and the latter asserting that emotions exist entirely in discourse; the former considering emotions as things that 'are' in our biology, the latter taking them to be things that we 'do' in our embodied social and discursive relationships with others.

Lupton argues convincingly for the importance of the discursive dimension of emotion, and its role in defining 'bodily experience' *as* emotion (1998: 24). This suggests that in principle, to fully understand the role of emotions in interactions with objects, Design research should be open to their discursive dimension. This could be both a challenge and an opportunity, as by attending to the language associated with the emotional aspect of physical interactions with objects design research can engage with the social/ cultural dimensions of those interactions. The discursive aspect of emotions relates strongly to their function in policing our social behaviour. Lupton identifies the role that pride and shame have as social regulators (1998:19) and illustrates this with reference to the functions of disgust – a relative of shame - that Miller identifies (1997). As he puts it "Above all, it [disgust] is a moral and social sentiment [...] it ranks people and things in a kind of cosmic ordering.' (1997: 2). Disgust provides the most compelling example of the relationship between physical feelings and what Lupton identifies as 'sociocultural processes', manifested in discourse (1998: 34).

It is notable that this negative emotion does not feature in much of the literature, either that from psychology or in design, despite its clear role in behaviour, including behaviour that

relates to designed objects (Fisher 2004, Kubberød 2005). Russell's influential 'circumplex' of emotions (1980) for instance includes negative emotional states such as 'alarmed', 'afraid', 'angry', 'frustrated', 'annoyed' and 'distressed', but not disgusted. This may be because it is difficult to consider disgust in the abstract – disgust is always disgust *at* something, as Miller stresses, because of its strongly embodied nature. It may be easier to ignore the 'referent' of the emotions listed above, though for each of them a referent is also logically necessary. With disgust it is impossible to ignore the 'to, from and about' of the emotion.

Studies of the emotional aspect of consumers' reception and evaluation of designs therefore seem to somewhat downplay the relational nature of emotions. This may derive from pressures to concentrate on the aspects of emotion that are likely to bring short term instrumentally applicable benefit – designers and companies want insights that can be applied and that can identify aspects of designs that are likely to elicit appropriate emotions, to make sales.

Empirical work

The authors were briefed to evaluate with consumers a range of novel food can shapes prior to the launch of a can with a 'waisted' outline – designed to package a low calorie food (Can number 3 in figure 1). The short timescale available ruled out the use of qualitative methods to discover the categories through which consumers were likely to engage with the can shapes. The potential however did exist to get insight into consumers' evaluation of the shapes in terms of categories connected to emotions. Because of the type of product intended for the can, the participants were limited to women only, between the ages of 20 and 45. The 12 shapes included a standard can – the ones shown in Figure 1 are those that are in the public domain.

Figure 1: Can shapes

Without being told of the intended function for can 3, the participants worked through a triadic construct elicitation technique (Kelly 1955) to identify their mental constructs about the shapes. This procedure uses Kelly's psychology of mental constructs, which favours neither cognition nor affect but ascribes actions and beliefs to mental constructs – the personal reference system through which individuals interpret the world (Kelly 1955, Fransella & Bannister 1989). Each construct is expressed as a dichotomy, for instance masculine/feminine or crisp/curvy. The participants then rate each shape against each construct to produce a grid of rating data. The correlations between the can shapes found in this data demonstrated that the participants rated similar shapes in a similar way, grouping similar cans together and distinguishing between groups of cans on the basis of their overall shapes and their details. For instance there was significant negative correlation between the standard can (number 2) and a group of the shaped cans.

As well as generating statistical data about the shapes, the elicited constructs also constitute a body of linguistic data that can be analysed qualitatively. Of the 104 constructs elicited, a majority, 64, were purely descriptive. These used words such as 'curved', 'grooved', 'straight' or 'ridged'. The prevalence of such terms indicates the mundane nature of the subject matter – tin cans, even shaped ones, are not highly salient in everyday life. A second group of words confirms that participants found it difficult to come up with *personal* constructs about the cans. This group of 14 constructs are similes describing the shapes in terms of objects such as a wineglass or a milk bottle. However, a third group of constructs, 25 in all, included words that have more richly inflected meaning.

This group of constructs includes:

curves, slender (x2), elegant, sophisticated, thin, tall, feminine (x2), hourglass (x2), waist (x3), curvy, soft, smooth, angular, masculine (x2), hard, bulky, chunky (x2), dumpy, squat (x2), fat at bottom, fat.

and confirm that the participants brought ideas about gender and body shape to their evaluation of the can shapes. This group includes words that have positive and negative connotations – ‘elegant’ is very different from ‘dumpy’ in the context of body shapes. Although this is evidence that these participants connected the can shapes with discourse about body shapes, these data do not allow us to go much beyond stating that fact. Had the research process been able to capture richer evidence about the participants’ relationship to discourses of femininity and body shape, say through interview, it might be possible to relate the constructs evident above to the emotion words discussed below.

The participants also rated the cans against four pairs of terms supplied to them. These were derived from an emotion circumplex based on Russell (1980). Russell established that it is possible to map the relationship of emotions to each other by positioning them on two axes – ‘arousal’ and ‘pleasantness’ (Figure 2), which he calls a ‘layman’s mental map’ of emotion (1980:1164). Russell notes that these terms are bipolar – they operate as dichotomies in the manner of Kelly’s mental constructs. Therefore it seemed safe to use emotion terms of this sort to rate the can shapes.

Figure 2 affect concept poles (Russell 1980)

Russell's circumplex and those proposed by others since (e.g. Watson and Tellegen 1985, Desmet et al 2000, 2001) have developed the basic emotion concepts expressed as nouns in Figure 2 into groups of emotion words that indicate subjective states. From these terms, four sets of polar opposites were selected for this study and the participants rated the can shapes against these. They were:

active – passive; unsettling – serene; lively – sluggish; delightful – gloomy

These terms were selected from the range of affect terms against two criteria: they were clear dichotomies and they seemed likely to relate to the can shapes. They also preserve much of the relationship they have in relation to Russell's two axes of arousal and value. There was no expectation that it would be possible to derive telling inter-correlations between the cans from these rankings when they were analysed together, as the qualities they describe, are intentionally distinct from each other. This turned out to be the case. Analysing the supplied construct rankings together produced no clear pattern in the correlations between the shapes and few correlations of extreme significance.

Taken supplied construct by supplied construct the correlations are somewhat more illuminating, but as expected, do not help to identify a relationship between the can shapes and the emotion circumplex. They do show that some of the cans correlate strongly with each

other, whichever pair of qualities they were being ranked against – the relationships largely following the same pattern as for the elicited constructs. For instance, cans which shared a distinctive feature correlated when ranked against the 'active/ passive' scale and the 'lively/ sluggish' scale. However the graphical representation of their ranking against these scales presented in figure 3 is more informative as it positions each shape in Russell's emotion space.

Adopting another of Russell's principles – that the centre of the circle is the neutral point on each axis and the edge of the circle is the point where the emotion is at its greatest intensity (1980: 1170) average scores were calculated for each shape against each axis and plotted on the circumplex (see figure 3). This indicated that some shapes have a distinct 'character' in terms of the emotion words used.

Can 1

Can 2

Can 3

Figure 3: Can ratings

Cans 1 and 3 were rated towards the positive emotions, with can 3 being markedly 'active', 'delightful' and 'lively'. This sets it apart from all the others in this emotion rating, as it was set apart in the construct correlations.

In contrast, can 2, as well as three other shapes in the set that were 'bottom heavy' were rated as markedly 'sluggish', 'passive', 'gloomy' and 'unsettling', though to a smaller degree. The distinctiveness of these two groups of shapes is reinforced by the fact that the ratings for the remaining shapes clustered round the neutral point.

These results seem to be a genuine evaluation of the shapes. A family relationship was evident in the groups of shapes that correlated with each other and the qualities these families shared matched the emotion words they tended towards on the circumplex. 1 and 3 have a degree of formal 'tension', whereas the regular can shape, number 2, along with others that it correlated with are relatively bottom-heavy and 'planted' in appearance. The extent to which the evaluations of the shapes genuinely relate to emotions that participants may feel

spontaneously in everyday life is, however, a matter of conjecture, given the lack of rich qualitative data to triangulate with these results. However, this absence serves the purpose of this paper as it points up the need to generate qualitative data to capture the discursive element of the emotions elicited by objects that are defined by ‘sociocultural processes’.

Discussion

It was not possible in the research just described to engage extensively with the ‘sociocultural processes’ that may be relevant to the discursive dimension of consumers’ affective evaluations of canned slimming food. The timescale and the client’s preference indicated a reductive approach that excluded obviously symbolic factors - labels, graphics, shelf placement etc. However, the results do imply that the participants were drawing on familiar discourses of health and beauty in their evaluations of the cans – though they were not directed towards these discourses in the process of the research. It seems safe to assume therefore that the participants read the shapes of the cans for such graphic/ symbolic associations as they might have. Can 3 for instance does have a ‘waist’ and reinforcing ribs that form a band round the shape add a ‘belt’ motif that cinches in the shape. This reference was obvious to the designers who referred to the shape as the ‘Marilyn’ can.

Recent research has suggested that women think about the shape and size of their bodies on average every fifteen minutes (Sayal 2006). Significant aspects of the participants’ ‘goals, standards and attitudes’ (Desmet et al 2001) are likely to derive from the very powerful values that western culture associates with body size and shape and these were therefore likely to have been highly salient to their evaluations of the can shapes. While this ‘concern’ was probably similar for all the participants it is not likely to have been uniform, given that women will come to their own accommodation with those values. It is safe to assume however, that the participants will have read the cans’ symbolic content in terms of these concerns while making their evaluation of the shapes in terms of the emotion words.

One potentially confounding aspect of the method described here is that it required that the participants translate between the verbal representations of feelings and their impressions of the shapes – they had to work between the verbal and the visual. Desmet’s emotion evaluation tool avoids this by adopting an entirely visual approach to evaluation, giving it potential cross cultural validity. However, it is positively useful in the case of the evaluation of design elements to preserve the linguistic dimension of our evaluation of objects in emotion terms because the discursive aspect of emotion *exists in language*.

Russell suggests that the same cognitive mechanism is at work when we are interpreting the emotions displayed by another person on their face, interpreting verbal or observed stimuli, or interpreting our own inner state. He also argues that the resulting interpretations all have the same relationship to each other on his circumplex.

"..the cognitive structure that is utilized in interpreting the meaning of verbal messages or of facial expressions from others is the same structure utilized in the process of conceptualising one's own state, which precedes the affective experience."
(1980: 1176)

So our interpretation of our embodied experience of our own emotions and the idea of emotions that are communicated by other people or by objects relies on the same mechanism. It seems reasonable to suppose then that in the interpretation of objects we use the same emotional 'expertise' as we do when interpreting our own physical feelings or the expressions of others – expertise gained and defined through the sociocultural processes that Lupton points to.

However, interpreting the indications of emotion in another person presumably differs from interpreting one's own state in that in the former physical feelings are absent, whereas in the latter one is interpreting one's own physical feelings. This means that some degree of 'projection' is involved in interpreting states in others – we have to imagine what we would feel like if we looked as the other looks, if we were making that face, adopting that posture etcetera in order to identify the relevant emotion. It seems reasonable to assume that the same mechanism is behind the evaluation of objects in emotion terms. Given our tendency to read objects as expressive of human or animal qualities (Ingram & Annable 2004), an anthropomorphic transformation might occur whereby the object is accorded active human properties that can be evaluated in terms that describe human emotions. In the example discussed above, the can is in effect given temporary human status to the extent that it matches the participant's understanding of the relationship between it and the emotions implied by the supplied constructs.

In their anthropomorphized form, the cans would act as shape exemplars against the 'expression' of which the participants measured the potential emotional content. However, given the importance of the normative sociocultural element of emotions, the cans would not simply act as exemplars for physical feelings, but also for the values commonly attached to those feelings (Lupton, 1997: 19). So a participant would ask not just, 'what would I be feeling like if I was that shape?', but also, perhaps, 'would being that shape and feeling that

feeling be desirable/ acceptable?’ The arbiter of desirability/ acceptability here, being the sociocultural ‘feeling rules’ that govern how we ‘do’ emotions about our bodies.

The rules invoked would differ depending on the emotion axis in question and this would require the symbolic content of the shape to provide the ‘referent’ for the emotion. So the ‘serenity’ perceived in can 1 and the ‘liveliness’ and ‘activeness’ perceived in can 3 would perhaps be tied down by a directly anthropomorphic relationship between the can shapes and stereotypically feminine body shape – the shapes operate as indexical signs of this body form. This circuit between shape, anthropomorphic identification with it and reading of it in terms that fit with the emotion terms used is completed by the ‘feeling rules’ (Hochschild 1983) provided by discourses of femininity and evident in the elicited constructs.

This in turn points up the significant shortcomings in an approach to product evaluation that is as reductive as the one described, for all that it did produce useful results. A procedure that integrated a rich qualitative element to capture the discursive aspect of the participants’ emotional relationship to the can shapes is likely to have exposed the relationship between the shapes and the difficult, contested issue of femininity and body shape. This is potentially of more than academic relevance as it is in the socio-cultural domain that the consequences of human/ object relationships may be challenged and reformed.

Conclusion

This paper has proposed insights are available into human relationships to objects by attending to the discursive aspect of emotions. It acknowledges both the opportunities that derive from investigating product details in these terms, and the desirability of attending to the social nature of emotions in this process. It discussed the strengths and weaknesses of research processes that take a reductive approach, acknowledging that such an approach can draw from well validated frameworks for emotion and can identify clear relationships between objects and emotions. However, to give full access to the discursive dimension of emotions elicited in human/ object interactions implies that qualitative methods should be used in combination with reductive ones.

It is notable that much design literature on emotion ignores the emotion that objects can elicit most unequivocally – disgust. This may indicate a desire to emphasise positive aspects of our relationships with objects given that disgust is the emotion that designers and manufacturers would probably least like to be associated with most of their products. But it is curious, given the insights into the embodied materiality of an interaction with an object that a very strong

negative emotion can provide. While this lacuna is understandable from a commercial perspective, it is not necessarily so useful for design. An approach to design and emotion that values *all* emotion – in the spirit of the ‘hedonics’ that is found in sensory studies of food might be more useful.

As Desmet, Overbeeke and Tax admit, (2001: 33) their work on emotion and design ‘begs steals and borrows’ methods from a range of disciplines. This paper adopts a similar (and in the author’s opinion healthy) catholic approach. Even though it has attended to objects that were ‘reduced’ in a sense – to shapes - it has demonstrated that it is possible to capture individuals’ evaluations of elements of objects through a method that matches this reduction in its concentration on their emotional consequences. However, the specific case considered has a definite relationship to issues of femininity, which are inscribed in discourse and it therefore points strongly towards a method that honours this socio-cultural dimension of emotions.

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